

Smirnova Elena Aleksandrovna,
Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of Finance and Credit Department,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINANCIAL AND CREDIT SUPPORT MECHANISM FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT

().

« » « ».

(

,),

).

The article addresses a relevant scientific and practical problem stemming from the lack of a comprehensive and methodologically coherent approach to financial and credit support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The purpose of the study is to develop an integrated mechanism capable of systematically combining heterogeneous financial sources, instruments, and institutional components, thereby enabling the transition from fragmented support measures to a structured system of managing financial stability and investment development in the SME sector.

The methodological framework of the research is based on systemic and comparative analysis, as well as methods of classification, structuring, and synthesis. This approach made it possible to conduct a critical review of existing theoretical interpretations of the categories «financial provision» and «financial mechanism», identifies the institutional and economic characteristics of SMEs, and formulates the author's conceptual vision of the structure of the proposed mechanism.

The study results in the development and visualization of a structural and functional model of the financial and credit mechanism for SME development. The model incorporates a goal-setting block, interrelated functional subsystems (financial relations management, financial resource and fund management, institutional interaction, resource support, risk management, etc.), as well as cross-cutting components such as public-private partnership, innovation support, digital financial tools, and monitoring and evaluation.

The main conclusion of the study is that the proposed mechanism forms a closed-loop management system that ensures coherence among state institutions, development agencies, and financial organizations, thereby creating conditions for sustainable and expanded SME development. The theoretical significance of the work lies in refining the conceptual framework and designing a holistic author's model of the mechanism, while its practical value is determined by the applicability of the findings in shaping effective SME support policies at national and regional levels.

Keywords: small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), financial and credit support, mechanism development, financial sustainability, government support, financing, development institutions, monitoring.

[4].

» [5].

[6].

-
1. - (. . .),
 2. - (. . . , . . . , . . .),
 3. (. . . , . . .),
 4. - (. . .),
 5. (. . .),
 6. (. . .),

1.

« »

(. . . , . . .)

1.

*

	-		/
.	- ,		-
.,	- ;	- ,	- ,
.	- -	-	- ,
.,	-	- ;	- -
.. -	-	-	- ,
..	-		
..	- ;		-
()	- -	- ,	-

*

[7-13]

2

2.

*

/ -		() -	/ -
-	,	,	-
	,	,	-
	,	,	-
-	,	,	-
-	-	-	,
-		,	-
-	,	,	-

*

1.

«
»[15].
«
»[16].
«
»[17].
«
»[18].
[9].
[19].
«
»[20].
[21, 22].
[23].
1. () ()
2. ,
3. ,

)
)
)
)

.2. () -

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

1. — 4(53). — 5-15. — DOI 10.37279/2312-5330-2020-4-5-15. — EDN STEIND.
2. — 1977. — 224 .
3. — 860 . — ISBN 978-5-8041-0336-2. — EDN QSWVNJ.
4. — 2000. — 512 .
5. — 2014. — 4(29). — 6-15. — EDN UZCSSB.
6. — 2012. — 492 .
7. — 2009. — 512 .
8. — 3- — 2000. — 207 .
9. — 2003. — 496 . — ISBN 5-16-001562-0. — EDN QQCCUX.
10. []: / [()]. — 1972. — 240 .
11. « », 2006. — 617 . — EDN TFVEEB.
12. []: « »/ — 3- — 2008. — 335 . — (). — ISBN 978-5-365-00910-3. — EDN QSVFTP.
13. []: — 1998. — 638 .

14. . . . // — 2018. — 6(36). — 204-207. — EDN VASUQE.
15. . . . : [. . . . / ,]; — : , 1997. — 477
16. . . . : / [.]; — : , 1991. — 276
17. . . . : / [.]; — : , 2009. — 870 . — ISBN 978-5-93763-010-0. — EDN QTLRQP.
18. . . . — 7- : / , « »», 2024. — 368 . — ISBN 978-5-406-13054-4. — EDN JKSFMA.
19. . . . [. . . .] : , / : , ; — : ; , 1998. — 412 .
20. . . . (. . . .) : / , [. . . .]; « - », 2007. — 601 . — (100) . — ISBN 978-5-16-002990-0. — EDN QSFVYP.
21. . . . / [.] . — 2. — : , 1999. — 557 .
22. . . . ; ; ; — : , 2016. — 347 . — EDN ZJITML.
23. . . . : / ; - , 2004. — 96 .

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Vorobyova, E. I. Finansovoe obespechenie ekonomicheskogo rosta na razlichnyh urovnayah ekonomiki v Rossijskoj Federacii / E. I. Vorobyova, O. G. Blazhevich // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2020. — 4(53). — S. 5-15. — DOI 10.37279/2312-5330-2020-4-5-15. — EDN STEIND.
2. Pessel', M.A. Finansovo-kreditnyj mekhanizm intensivizacii obshchestvennogo proizvodstva / M.A. Pessel'. — Moskva: Finansy, 1977. — 224 s.
3. Bol'shoj ekonomicheskij slovar': ekonomika, finansy, buhuchet, nalogi, strahovanie, marketing, menedzhment, upravlenie / avt. i sost. A. B. Borisov. — Izd. 2-e, pererab. i dop.. — Moskva: Knizhnyj mir, 2009. — 860 s. — ISBN 978-5-8041-0336-2. — EDN QSWVNJ.
4. Blank I.A. Upravlenie formirovaniem kapitala / I.A. Blank. — K.: Nika-Centr, 2000. — 512 s.
5. Vorobyov, Yu. N. Finansovoe obespechenie hozyajstvennoj deyatelnosti organizacij v usloviyah nestabil'nosti rynkov / Yu. N. Vorobyov // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2014. — 4(29). — S. 6-15. — EDN UZCSSB.
6. Finansovoe obespechenie social'no-ekonomicheskogo razvitiya regiona: monografiya / G.G. Ermolenko, M.S. Abibullaev, G.D. Bodner i dr.; pod red. G.G. Ermolenko, M.Yu. Kussogo. — Simferopol': IT «ARIAL», 2012. — 492 s.
7. Balabanov, I. T. Osnovy finansovogo menedzhmenta. Kak upravlyat' kapitalom / I. T. Balabanov. — M.: Finansy i statistika, 2009. — 512 s.
8. Metodika finansovogo analiza: uchebnoe i prakticheskoe posobie / A. D. SHERemet, R. S. Sajfulin, E. V. Negashev. — 3-e izd., pererab. i dop. — Moskva: INFRA-M, 2000. — 207 s.
9. Kovaleva, A. M. Finansy firmy: Uchebnyj dlya studentov vuzov, obuchayushchihsya po ekonomicheskim special'nostyam i napravleniyam / A. M. Kovaleva, M. G. Lapusta, L. G. Skamaj. — 3-e izdanie, ispravlennoe i dopolnennoe. — Moskva: INFRA-M, 2003. — 496 s. — ISBN 5-16-001562-0. — EDN QQCCUX.
10. Finansovyj mekhanizm vozdejstviya na proizvodstvo [Tekst]: Na primere prom-sti SSSR i NRB / [Pod obshch. red. professorov M. S. Atlas i R. D. Vinokur]; Mosk. fin. in-t (SSSR). Svishtov. vyssh. fin.-hoz. in-t im. D. Cenova (NRB). — Moskva: Finansy, 1972. — 240 s.
11. Bol'shakov, S. V. Finansy predpriyatij: teoriya i praktika: uchebnyj / S. V. Bol'shakov. — Moskva: Izdatel'stvo «Knizhnyj mir», 2006. — 617 s. — EDN TFVEEB.
12. Karaseva, I. M. Finansovyj menedzhment: [upravlenie dvizheniem denezhnyh sredstv, informacionnoe obespechenie finansovogo menedzhmenta, nalogovoe planirovanie na predpriyatii, finansovyj menedzhment i audit]: uchebnoe posobie po specializacii «Menedzhment organizacii» / I. M. Karaseva; I. M. Karaseva, M. A. Revyakina;

pod red. Yu. P. Aniskina. — 3-e izd., ster.. — Moskva : Omega-L, 2008. — 335 s. — (Vysshaya shkola menedzhmenta). — ISBN 978-5-365-00910-3. — EDN QSVFTP.

13. Pavlova L. N. *Finansy predpriyatij* [Tekst] : ucheb. dlya studentov vuzov, obuchayushchihsya po ekon. spec. / L. N. Pavlova. — Moskva : Finansy: YUniti, 1998. — 638 s.

14. Gusejnova, G. M. *Finansovoe obespechenie predpriyatij: sushchnost', osnovnye principy* / G. M. Gusejnova, A. Yu. Bystrickaya // *Teoriya i praktika sovremennoj nauki*. — 2018. — 6(36). — S. 204-207. — EDN VASUQE.

15. *Finansy. Denezhnoe obrashchenie. Kredit*: [Ucheb. dlya ekon. special'nostej vuzov / L. A. Drobozina, L. P. Okuneva, L. D. Androsova i dr.]; Pod red. L. A. Drobozinoj. — Moskva : Finansy, 1997. — 477 s.

16. *Gosudarstvennye finansy: Ucheb. posobie dlya studentov ekon. vuzov i fak.* / [V. M. Fedosov i dr.]; Pod red. V. M. Fedosova i dr. — Kiev : Lybid', 1991. — 276 s.

17. *Ekonomicheskaya teoriya. Politekonomiya* : uchebnik / [V. D. Bazilevich i dr.]; pod red. V. D. Bazilevicha. — Moskva : Rybari, 2009. — 870 s. — ISBN 978-5-93763-010-0. — EDN QTLRQP.

18. Lavrushin, O. I. *Bankovskoe delo: sovremennaya sistema kreditovaniya* / O. I. Lavrushin, O. N. Afanas'eva. — 7-e izdanie, pererabotannoe i dopolnennoe. — Moskva : Obshchestvo s ogranichennoj otvetstvennost'yu «Izdatel'stvo "KnoRus"», 2024. — 368 s. — ISBN 978-5-406-13054-4. — EDN JKSFMA.

19. *Finansy predpriyatij* [Tekst] : ucheb. dlya studentov vuzov, obuchayushchihsya po ekon. spec. / kol. avt.: N. V. Kolchina, G. B. Polyak, L. P. Pavlova i dr.; pod red. prof. N. V. Kolchinoj. — Moskva : Finansy: YUNITI, 1998. — 412 s.

20. *Ekonomika predpriyatiya (firmy)* : uchebnik / O. I. Volkov, O. V. Devyatkin, N. B. Akulenko [i dr.]; Pod redakciej professora O. I. Volkova i docenta O. V. Devyatkina. — 3-e izdanie, pererabotannoe i dopolnennoe. — Moskva : Izdatel'skij Dom «Infra-M», 2007. — 601 s. — (100 let REA im. G.V. Plekhanova). — ISBN 978-5-16-002990-0. — EDN QSFVYP.

21. *Spravochnik finansista predpriyatiya* / [Barannikova N.P. i dr.]. — 2. izd., dop. i pererab. — Moskva : INFRA-M, 1999. — 557 s.

22. *Enciklopedicheskij slovar' ekonomicheskikh i finansovykh terminov, ponyatij i opredelenij* / Ministerstvo obrazovaniya i nauki RF; CHelyabinskij gosudarstvennyj universitet; Institut ekonomiki otraslej, biznesa i administrirovaniya; pod obshchej redakciej V.I. Barhatova. — CHelyabinsk : CHelyabinskij gosudarstvennyj universitet, 2016. — 347 s. — EDN ZJITML.

23. Oparin, Yu. A. *Finansy i kredit promyshlennosti* : ucheb. posobie / Yu. A. Oparin ; M-vo obrazovaniya i nauki Ros. Federacii, Om. gos. tekhn. un-t. — Omsk : Izd-vo OmGTU, 2004. — 96 s.

18 2025

2 2025